

NEW GENOMIC TECHNIQUES
NEW FOOD SYSTEMS

ATTENTION! SCIENCE IN PROGRESS:
Analytical detection of NGTs in
food and feed is achievable – and
essential to maintain trust and
transparency

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Executive summary

Widely used PCR-based methods, including qPCR and dPCR, remain highly effective tools for detecting genetically modified organisms (GMOs) in food and feed. These techniques are already mastered by enforcement laboratories across Europe and can be adapted to detect NGTs—provided there is basic prior knowledge about the specific genetic modification being investigated. This is known as *targeted detection*.

Sequencing-based methods, including untargeted and semi-targeted approaches, offer promising new capabilities for identifying NGTs. However, these methods are not yet routinely used in official GMO control settings and require further development and validation before widespread adoption.

The DARWIN project recently published a groundbreaking study demonstrating the feasibility of creating a unique “genetic fingerprint” to identify a specific NGT line. This fingerprint is made up of multiple genetic features and can be detected using a range of methods—from targeted PCR to advanced sequencing techniques. The study represents a major step forward in the detection and traceability of gene-edited organisms.

Access to details on specific modifications and the genetic background of NGT lines would make detection strategies more effective. Transparency would simplify investigations, cut costs, and speed up analysis. This would help regulators and the food system. Public investment in genomic databases covering full species diversity, along with clear legal rules requiring data disclosure by developers, is essential for progress.

Glossary

NGTs (New Genomic Techniques)	A group of advanced methods, including CRISPR/Cas, used to edit the genomes of organisms with high precision ¹ .
NGT line	A specific organism that has been modified using new genomic techniques.
DNA (Deoxyribonucleic Acid)	The molecule that carries genetic instructions in all living organisms. DNA is made up of four chemical bases: adenine (A), thymine (T), cytosine (C), and guanine (G). These bases pair in specific ways (A with T, C with G) to form the double helix structure of DNA.
RNA (Ribonucleic Acid)	A molecule similar to DNA that plays a key role in gene expression and protein production. Unlike DNA, RNA uses uracil (U) instead of thymine and is typically single-stranded.
CRISPR/Cas	A modern gene-editing tool that allows scientists to make precise ¹ changes to DNA by cutting and modifying specific sequences.
TALENS (Transcription Activator-Like Effector Nucleases)	An older gene-editing tool that allows targeted changes to DNA, similar to CRISPR/Cas.
PCR (polymerase chain reaction)	A technique used to make millions of copies of a specific DNA segment, enabling its detection and analysis.
dPCR (digital PCR)	A DNA testing method that divides a sample into thousands of tiny reactions, allowing for highly accurate measurement of specific genetic material.

¹ While genomic edits can be performed with high precision, it is well known in the scientific literature that unintended off-target effects may also occur.

RT-qPCR (real-time quantitative PCR)	A widely used method to detect and measure DNA in real time, often used in GMO testing.
GMO (Genetically Modified Organism)	An organism whose genetic material has been altered using biotechnology to introduce new traits.
GE (Genome-Edited)	Refers to organisms that have undergone specific genetic changes using tools like CRISPR/Cas, often considered a subset of GMOs.
Genetic fingerprint	A unique combination of genetic features that can be used to identify a specific organism or GMO.
SNV (Single-Nucleotide Variation)	A change in a single DNA building block (nucleotide), which can be used to distinguish between different genetic lines.
WGS (Whole-Genome Sequencing)	A method that reads the entire DNA sequence of an organism, giving a comprehensive view of its genetic code.
Metagenomic sequencing	A technique that sequences all DNA in a mixed sample (e.g., processed food) to identify the organisms present and provide at least partial genomic information for them.
Amplicon sequencing	A method that sequences only specific regions of DNA that have been targeted and amplified using PCR.
Bioinformatics	The use of computer tools to analyse biological data, such as DNA sequences, often essential for interpreting results from sequencing.
Targeted detection	A testing approach that looks for specific, known genetic changes using methods like qPCR or dPCR.
Untargeted detection	A broader approach that scans the entire genome or sample without prior knowledge of specific changes, often using sequencing.

Transgene	A gene that has been artificially introduced into an organism, typically from another species.
PAM (Protospacer Adjacent Motif)	A short DNA sequence required for CRISPR/Cas to recognise and cut the target DNA.
ENGL (European Network of GMO Laboratories)	A network of official laboratories in the EU that develop and validate methods for GMO detection.
MPR (Minimum Performance Requirements for GMO Detection)	A set of technical standards established by the European Network of GMO Laboratories (ENGL) to ensure that GMO detection methods used in official controls are reliable, sensitive, and fit for purpose.

Introduction

Genome-editing technologies such as TALENS and, most impactful, CRISPR/Cas, came on the scene around 2010-2012 and are referred to as “new genomic techniques”, or NGTs for short. As with many **new technologies**, these innovations bring **new regulatory challenges**. In some cases, the genetic changes introduced are challenging to detect using current technologies. This poses a problem to existing EU standards of transparency, traceability, and labelling of food and feed products—requirements strongly supported by most consumers, farmers, civil society organisations and many actors in the food industry².

In the **European Union**, the release of genetically modified organisms (GMOs) into the environment and the food chain have been regulated under Directive 2001/18/EC³ and Regulations 1829/2003⁴ and 1830/2003⁵. These laws mandate traceability throughout the supply chain and require clear labelling. Traceability is ensured through legal obligations requiring operators to document the presence and types of GMOs throughout the supply chain and is complemented by the use of detection methods. Together, these pieces of legislation uphold the EU’s standards for biosafety and consumer transparency, while also enabling post-market monitoring and the withdrawal of products found to pose risks to human health or the environment. At the **international level**, living GMOs fall under the Cartagena Protocol on Biosafety to the Convention on Biological Diversity (Article 11)⁶.

To overcome these challenges, the European Commission issued calls for projects to explore the **development of detection methods for NGTs**. As a result, two research projects funded by the EU research programme Horizon Europe, **DARWIN** and **DETECTIVE**,

² For example, see <https://www.ohnegentechnik.org/en/press/articles/european-enterprises-call-for-rigorous-labelling-of-ngts>

³ Directive 2001/18/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 March 2001 on the deliberate release into the environment of genetically modified organisms and repealing Council Directive 90/220/EEC - Commission Declaration; <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2001/18/oj/eng>

⁴ Regulation (EC) No 1829/2003 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 September 2003 on genetically modified food and feed; <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2003/1829/oj/eng>

⁵ Regulation (EC) No 1830/2003 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 September 2003 concerning the traceability and labelling of genetically modified organisms and the traceability of food and feed products produced from genetically modified organisms and amending Directive 2001/18/EC; <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2003/1830/oj/eng>

⁶ Text of the Cartagena Protocol on Biosafety; <https://bch.cbd.int/protocol/text>

are leading the way in developing new analytical detection methods specifically tailored to NGTs. In parallel, DARWIN is also developing the digital technologies needed to securely and reliably store, track and trace NGT products throughout the supply chain, from seed to shelf.

What makes new detection methods essential for NGT products?

The current analytical framework for detection of GMOs relies on methods such as real-time quantitative polymerase chain reaction (qPCR) and, more recently, digital PCR (dPCR). These PCR-based methods target specific DNA sequences from GMOs, allowing scientists to detect and quantify their presence in food and feed products.

This strategy is highly effective in identifying and quantifying *known* GMOs created using earlier genetic engineering techniques. Under EU legislation, developers are required to provide the genetic information that allows official laboratories to design and validate detection methods (Regulation 1829/2003, Articles 5(3)(i) and 17(3)(i); Regulation 1830/2003, Article 4(1) and Recital 8 of the preamble).

This detection strategy revolves around utilising commonly used genetic elements to identify GMOs. However, NGTs present new challenges:

- **NGTs do not introduce common genetic elements into the genome.** Without this typical “genetic baggage” to target, efficient screening is hampered.
- **CRISPR/Cas can be used to make distinct modifications at multiple sites across the genome simultaneously.** Traditional PCR methods usually target one or a few specific DNA sequences, meaning separate reactions may be needed for each site. This approach is time-consuming, resource-intensive, and prone to inconsistency across reactions. New methods that allow simultaneous detection of multiple targets are needed to address this complexity.
- **The genetic changes introduced by NGTs can be extremely small—sometimes involving just a single DNA nucleotide.** This makes them harder to detect using conventional PCR methods, which were primarily designed to identify the larger insertions typical of traditional GMOs. As a result, subtle modifications from NGTs are more difficult to detect, and new approaches are needed when developing qPCR methods to effectively identify them.
- **Unintended or “off-target” changes can appear in the genome with NGTs, but these changes differ from those caused by older genetic engineering methods.** These changes can sometimes be used to detect NGT products. However, newer techniques may create no off-target changes at all. This leaves fewer signals to look for, making it

harder to confirm whether a product or mixture contains GMOs.

These and additional challenges, along with DARWIN’s approach to addressing them are shown in **TABLE 1**.

TABLE 1. Main advancements in DARWIN

CHALLENGES FOR NGT DETECTION AND MARKET CONTROL	DARWIN AMBITION AND APPROACH
Current PCR-based methods do not allow reliable detection/quantification of NGT mutations	Develop enhanced targeted methods using next-gen PCR and amplicon sequencing; evaluate their compliance with minimum performance requirements (MPR) set by the European Union Reference Laboratory for Genetically Modified Food and Feed
Common transgene sequences for screening do not exist in NGT	Sequencing methods are being developed to screen key genetic elements
Distinguishing more minor or undisclosed NGT modifications from natural variation or other genetic engineering methods may not be achievable	Genetic fingerprints are generated to unambiguously identify a specific NGT line using sequencing and machine learning tools + a database of genome sequences covering the full genetic species diversity
Only known NGT lines are detectable	Untargeted sequencing methods (WGS and metagenomics) are being explored to identify known and unknown NGT lines

Dedicated research on detection method development—and, critically, the funding for this research—has only recently begun with projects like DARWIN. Ensuring that robust analytical methods are in place is essential for evidence-based policymaking around NGTs. The first steps are to explore what is possible on a technical level. Based on the results, the most effective detection protocols can then be further developed.

DARWIN's approach to developing next-generation detection methods

First, as for classical GMO detection strategies, DARWIN focuses on DNA-based methods rather than protein- or RNA-based ones because DNA provides a direct link to the genetic modification event itself and is less likely to degrade during food processing—a clear advantage in this context.

Next, within the field of DNA-based detection methods, DARWIN is exploring two main approaches:

1. **Targeted**, requiring some prior knowledge on specific known sequences from GMOs within a sample and mainly based on PCR technologies.
2. **Untargeted**, mainly based on sequencing technologies where all the DNA present within a sample is sequenced without prior knowledge of the sample. The explored high-throughput sequencing strategies include whole-genome sequencing and “metagenomic” sequencing.

Both approaches have their advantages and limitations.

Targeted methods require prior knowledge of the modification and a method developed for each specific case. They work well if the sample to be analysed is known and the genetic targets are clear. But in mixtures, or if an NGT line includes many genetic modifications spread across the whole genome, targeted methods become impractical.

Untargeted methods are universal. They sequence all the DNA in a sample without needing a specific method for each case. Their success depends on comprehensive sequence databases that include the specific modifications, the genetic background of NGTs, and the full diversity of the species.

Finally, what products are being used as test cases in the DARWIN project? DARWIN has strategically chosen rice and tomato—two model plant species that rank among the top 15 most valuable crops and livestock products due to their broad agricultural relevance⁷. These crops also top the list of genome-edited plant species, with over

300 edited rice lines and more than 100 tomato lines⁸. The detection methods and protocols being developed by DARWIN are tested on both pure rice and tomato products, as well as on processed and mixed products, such as tomato juice and multi-grain noodles containing rice (TABLE 2).

TABLE 2. DARWIN methods

METHOD(S)	SCOPE	TEST ORGANISMS / MIXTURES
Enhanced real-time (RT)-qPCR	Specific identification of SNP sequences Enhanced stability and nuclease resistance	NGT rice NGT tomato NGT tomato juice & mixtures
Triplex RT-qPCR	Specific identification of SNP sequences Improved multiplexing capacity (multi-target)	NGT tomato double mutant Tomato juice & mixtures
Duplex Droplet dPCR + Pentaplex nanoplate dPCR	Enhanced specificity & quantification Improved multiplexing capacity (multi-target)	NGT rice
PCR-enriched multi-target sequencing	Enhanced specificity Improved multiplexing capacity (multi-target)	NGT tomato NGT tomato juice and mixtures
Whole-genome sequencing (WGS)	Detection of known and unknown NGT lines in pure products and mixtures	NGT rice NGT tomato
Metagenomic high-throughput sequencing	Screen key genetic elements in pure products and mixtures	Mixtures of NGT and non-NGT rice seeds and noodles Mixtures of NGT rice seeds and other foods

⁸ EU-SAGE database. Available at: <https://www.eu-sage.eu/genome-search>

Targeted methods – Enhanced PCR-based approaches for sensitive and specific NGT detection

The DARWIN project is developing and testing several **targeted methods** that will expand what is possible in analytical detection using PCR-based approaches. A more detailed summary of the methods is given below, but first: Why is DARWIN exploring so many method variations? What is the expected outcome?

First, there are distinct cases of genomic modification using NGTs. For example, is there a single genetically modified sequence (target) in a single genomic region, or multiple sequences/regions? Different targeted methods, alone or in combination, will be better suited to these distinct cases.

Second, it is inevitable that some methodologies will turn out to be more promising than others. But this cannot be known in advance. Identifying a range of promising approaches in advance, and then testing them in the lab, significantly increases the likelihood of developing methods that work in real-world settings.

Now, **what is new in DARWIN's approach to targeted PCR-based methods tailored to NGT products?** The keywords here are **specificity** and **sensitivity**, as well as **multi-target**—the ability to detect multiple targets at once. The key targeted methods and their potential advantages are:

- **Advanced qPCR techniques** with specialised molecular probes to detect very small genetic changes—specifically, single-nucleotide modifications—in gene-edited rice and tomato samples. Additionally, qPCR methods designed to detect multiple genetic targets at the same time improve efficiency when screening for several modifications in a single test.
- **Digital PCR (dPCR)** offers several advantages over traditional qPCR. Unlike qPCR, dPCR can estimate the number of DNA copies with high precision, without needing pre-characterised DNA samples used for calibration, making it especially useful for detecting genetically modified sequences. It also performs more reliably in the presence of PCR inhibitors, or substances in the sample that might interfere with the test. These methods—designed to detect two (duplex) or five (pentaplex) genetic targets at once—will be applied to identify specific modifications in gene-edited rice.
- **Combined PCR and next-generation sequencing** to detect a wide range of genetic modifications without relying on traditional probe-based systems. This approach allows many gene-edited changes to be identified in a single test, making it especially useful for high-throughput screening of multiple NGT events at once.

Untargeted methods – Screening, detection, and identification of NGT lines with or without prior knowledge

DARWIN is developing and testing untargeted sequencing methods fit for different real-world scenarios:

- **Whole-genome sequencing (WGS) for characterisation of pure NGT lines**

This method reads the entire DNA sequence of a plant that has been developed using new genomic techniques (NGTs). It provides a complete picture of all genetic changes, including both intended edits and any unintended ones. WGS is especially useful when working with pure, unprocessed samples, such as seeds or laboratory-grown plants.

- **Metagenomic high-throughput sequencing for characterisation of mixtures, including processed food**

This approach is designed for complex samples that contain DNA from multiple sources—such as processed foods made from several ingredients. Instead of targeting specific genes, it sequences all the DNA present in the sample. Advanced computer analysis (bioinformatics) is then used to identify which genetic modifications are present and to determine whether any of them match known NGT lines.

All these sequencing approaches rely on subsequent **bioinformatic analysis** of the sequenced genomic data to identify NGT lines with statistical confidence. While several robust bioinformatic tools already exist, they must be adapted and optimised to detect the specific genes or sequences associated with NGTs. These advancements will not only support regulatory needs but also contribute valuable resources to the broader scientific community.

Hot off the press! The first results from DARWIN

DARWIN researchers and their collaborators published a breakthrough [scientific paper](#) in *Food Research International* on 5 August 2025, as part of the project's endeavour to develop detection methods for both known and unknown NGTs. The work presented in their article, titled '*Genetic fingerprints derived from genome database mining allow accurate identification of genome-edited rice in the food chain via targeted high-throughput sequencing*', is an exciting proof of concept for next-generation detection methods.

The authors combined several of the methods described above—including both targeted and untargeted approaches as well as bioinformatics and machine learning—to demonstrate that a unique *genetic fingerprint* can be generated for a specific organism. This fingerprint is based on detecting a distinct combination of single-nucleotide variations (SNVs) using a technique they call *targeted high-throughput sequencing*. As a proof of concept, they chose a genome-edited (GE) rice line that had only a single DNA base pair modified compared to the wild type.

To develop this fingerprinting strategy, the researchers used whole-genome sequencing data alongside publicly available genome databases and machine learning tools. Their goal was to identify and combine key genetic features that could reliably distinguish a specific GE rice line from all others. These features included the intended edit site, DNA sequences associated with the CRISPR/Cas editing process (known as PAM sites), possible unintended changes elsewhere in the genome (off-target effects), and naturally occurring genetic differences specific to certain rice varieties. By integrating these elements, the researchers were able to construct a unique and highly specific genetic fingerprint. See **FIGURE 1** for a visual representation of the overall process.

This innovative study marks an important step forward in ensuring reliable traceability of new GMOs within the food system. However, the authors emphasise that their approach currently depends on access to “precise and detailed sequence information on the genomic background,” as well as comprehensive databases of known cultivars and varieties. This highlights the need for continued public investment in genomic databases and for legal requirements that ensure developers of GMOs disclose at least a minimum level of genetic information about their NGT lines to support effective detection and monitoring.

FIGURE 1. Figure adapted from Fraiture et al. 2025, <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S096399692501556X>

Policy Recommendations

Detection methods for NGT products are feasible—especially when developers of these GMOs provide the necessary genetic data, as required under the current EU legislation (Directive 2001/18/EC and Regulations 1829/2003 and 1830/2003). Continued compliance with these requirements will help enforcement laboratories adapt existing PCR-based protocols for NGT detection.

It is possible to develop unique “genetic fingerprints” for specific NGT crops, enabling their unambiguous identification using targeted and/or untargeted detection methods. This approach strengthens traceability and supports regulatory oversight.

Reliable detection methods are essential to complement documentation-based traceability systems, ensuring transparency in the food chain and maintaining consumer trust. Achieving this will require sustained investment in research and infrastructure.

While the costs of implementing some of these new detection technologies on a per-sample basis will be high at this early stage, continued public and private investment is crucial to refine, validate, and scale up these methods, which will likely lead to breakthroughs in multiple areas of genomic and bioinformatic sciences. As with previous advances in sequencing technologies, costs are expected to decrease significantly over time—especially for the most promising and widely adopted approaches.

Mandating that developers of NGTs disclose a minimum level of genetic information would significantly reduce the cost and complexity of detection for enforcement authorities and food and feed operators. This would also accelerate the development of robust, science-based monitoring systems.

About DARWIN

As discussed in the Introduction, there are currently scientific and technological barriers to detecting and identifying products obtained through New Genomic Techniques. Under the existing EU GMO regulations, this causes ambiguity and uncertainty for producers, law enforcement authorities, and for consumers. DARWIN is a Horizon Europe project funded by the European Commission to co-develop a new generation of detection strategies for products obtained through NGTs, as well as innovative digital tracking and tracing solutions. These new methodologies and tools will contribute to a more sustainable, fair and transparent food system.

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